

The N-Token Concept.

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Abstract. This development paper presents an algorithm which expresses characters, 'A', 'B', 'Z' as single tokens. Each character has an index chosen by two parties, e.g: A=428, B=422.

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1 Introduction

LLMs have for a long-time struggled with multi-width characters in their transformers architecture. This paper aim to address to current gaps present in such transformers by introducing an algorithm which divide multi-width characters into digestable chunks.

2 Theorem 1

We shall introduce the following algorithm of A-Indices. Let the following algorithm for indices elements in an A-Base:

$$\text{AAlgorithm}(C) = \text{AGroup}_{low}(C_{low}) + \text{AGroup}_{high}(C_{high}) \quad (1)$$

$$\forall x \in \mathbb{R}, x > 1 \quad (2)$$

Where x is the A-Base index. An AAlgorithm(0) is an invalid index. Each element x shall be divisible by a power of two. An AAlgorithm is an algorithm used to encode an index to 'A-Code'.

3 Theorem 2

Let a set of AAlgorithm(x) be elements of an 'A-Code' alphabet. From a start index to an end index. An AAlgorithm(x) should be non-zero and continuous in the 'A-Code' set.

4 Applications: Hiragana Characters

After laying the two theorems, we will use the following Python script:

```
1 if __name__ == '__main__':
2     print("prompter.py <lang> <instructions>")
3
4     with open(sys.argv[1]) as f:
5         s = f.read()
6         s = s[s.find('---'):]
7         res = pytoklib.ntoken.ntoken(s,
8             pytoklib.sa1)
9         for vi in res:
10            print(vi[0])
11            print(vi[1])
12
13            with open(sys.argv[2]) as f2:
14                prompt = f2.read()
15                final = res
16                final += prompt
17                print(final)
18            with open("output.txt", "w") as f3:
19                f3.write(str(final))
```

The library is a work in progress, and is not implemented fully as described in the paper.

5 Conclusion

Concluding the paper with this approach could be useful when dealing with large, multi-width characters.